

1

Supplementary Material

2

Origins and diversification of the Caatinga dry forest endemic birds

3 HEVANA ^{1,5}, GUSTAVO A. BRAVO^{2,3}, DIEGO ASTÚA⁴, DANIELE MARIZ ⁵, SCOTT

4 EDWARDS², AND LUCIANO N. NAKA⁵

5

6 **Figure S1.** Distribution of the Caatinga endemic bird species used in the biogeographic analyses.
 7 On gray the current distribution of each taxon, based on the BirdLife International shapefiles
 8 (<https://datazone.birdlife.org/>), orange indicates the Caatinga area.

10

11

12

13 **Figure S2.** Plot of the Tinamidae phylogeny used in this study (Almeida et al. (2022)). The tips of the
 14 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 15 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

17 **Figure S3.** Plot of the Caprimulgidae phylogeny used in this study (White et al. (2016)). The tips of the
 18 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 19 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

21 **Figure S4.** Plot of the Picidae phylogeny used in this study (Shakya et al. (2017)). The tips of the
 22 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 23 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

25 **Figure S5.** Plot of the Psittacidae phylogeny used in this study (Selvatti et al. (2022)). The tips of the
 26 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 27 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

29 **Figure S6.** Plot of the Thamnophilidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 30 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 31 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

33 **Figure S7.** Plot of the Thamnophilidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 34 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 35 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

37 **Figure S8.** Plot of the Thamnophilidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 38 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 39 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

41 **Figure S9.** Plot of the Thamnophilidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 42 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 43 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

45 **Figure S10.** Plot of the Thamnophilidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 46 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 47 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

49 **Figure S11.** Plot of the Grallaridae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 50 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 51 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

53
 54
 55
 56
 57

58 **Figure S12.** Plot of the Rhinocryptidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 59 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 60 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

62 **Figure S13.** Plot of the Scleruridae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 63 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 64 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

66 **Figure S14.** Plot of the Dendrocolaptidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of
 67 the phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely
 68 ancestral area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

70 **Figure S15.** Plot of the Dendrocolaptidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of
 71 the phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely
 72 ancestral area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

74 **Figure S16.** Plot of the Dendrocolaptidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of
 75 the phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely
 76 ancestral area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

82 **Figure S18.** Plot of the Furnaridae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 83 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 84 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

86 **Figure S19.** Plot of the Furnaridae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 87 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 88 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

90 **Figure S20.** Plot of the Furnariidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 91 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 92 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

94 **Figure S21.** Plot of the Tyrannidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 95 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 96 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

98 **Figure S22.** Plot of the Tyrannidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 99 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 100 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

102 **Figure S23.** Plot of the Tyrannidae phylogeny used in this study (Harvey et al. (2020)). The tips of the
 103 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 104 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

106 **Figure S24.** Plot of the Troglodytidae phylogeny used in this study (Mann et al. (2006)). The tips of the
 107 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 108 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

110 **Figure S25.** Plot of the Passerelidae phylogeny used in this study (Barker et al. (2015). The tips of the
 111 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 112 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

114 **Figure S26.** Plot of the Icteridae phylogeny used in this study (Barker et al. (2015)). The tips of the
 115 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 116 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

118 **Figure S27.** Plot of the Icteridae phylogeny used in this study (Barker et al. (2015)). The tips of the
 119 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 120 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

122 **Figure S28.** Plot of the Thraupidae phylogeny used in this study (Barker et al. (2015)). The tips of the
 123 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 124 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

126 **Figure S29.** Plot of the Thraupidae phylogeny used in this study (Barker et al. (2015)). The tips of the
 127 phylogenies indicate the current species distributions, while internodes represent the most likely ancestral
 128 area distribution inferred by BioGeoBEARS.

129

130